

The Strategy to Build Educative Interaction in Islamic Education on Online Learning Setting

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Abstract

Nowadays, online learning has forced educational stakeholders to sufficiently involve online learning by handling the fundamental difference from traditional learning platforms. While educative interaction is vital but very limited to online learning, the teachers should condition the new environment to enable the learning process. However, educative interaction on online learning requires exact syntax to help the teachers implement it correctly. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the implementation of educative learning on online learning and formulate the syntax to help teachers create educative interaction. The study focused on Islamic and Character Education subjects. The research method is qualitative, using in-depth interviews to gather the data. The informants were from 2 different elementary schools. The study result revealed two types of syntax for educative interaction on online learning: the syntax of educative interaction on real-time chatting app and syntax of educative interaction on the video conference app. Every syntax has similar general phases: preparation, introduction, core, and closing. However, every phase has different details, adjusted to the service provided by the application used. Eventually, the teachers' competence and spirit and supporting infrastructure become the primary factors in maximizing the interaction. Besides, application choice determines the strategy that will be done.

Keywords: Online Educative Interaction, Online Learning, Online Learning Syntax, Islamic Education

INTRODUCTION

Technology breakthrough has presented online technology that is impactful for every part of human life, including education (Priatmoko, 2018: 232). Meanwhile, dependency on and bonding nowadays' students is inevitable (Ally, 2019; Sakti, 2020). Students in this digital era are more motivated (Komalasari & Saripudin, 2017: 184; Mertasari, 2016: 686; Sumardianta & Kris, 2018) and more likely to imitate any behavior that appeared on online technology (Ormiston, 2011; Panigrahi, Srivastava, & Sharma, 2018: 7). Therefore, the certainty of online technology enforces educational stakeholders to sufficiently involve online learning (Ally, 2019; Jensen, 2016: 13), one of which presents interesting and fun educative interaction.

Educative interaction is a reciprocal relationship between teachers and students in systematic learning to reach its objectives (Sardiman, 2014 as cited in Hayati, Noer, & Khoirol, 2015: 118). The educative interaction contains interactive unsure conditioning students' potential development in rational, humanist, and dialogic ways (Mollah, 2015: 255). Thereby, educative interaction proceeds in full of meaningful activities because it contains new norms that the teachers should transfer to the students (Lestari, 2017).

Educative interaction is conducted directly face-to-face. Along with technology development, educative interaction can be implemented through online learning (Harasim, 2002; Rovai, 2004). The interaction on online learning has different characteristics from the traditional class (Bowers & Kumar, 2015; Hass & Joseph, 2018). The fundamental difference is on the distant location between the teachers and the students and utilize internet networks for the interaction (Anderson, 2011; Mustofa, Chodzirin, & Sayekti,

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Kattani, 2019: 61). The approach is expected to nurture self-control, such as feel guilty when doing deviation (Josephson & Hanson, 2004: 4), and to nurture honesty, integrity, and responsibility (Schuller, 2004: 51). So, students can be motivated to be earnest and enthusiastic in carrying out assignments or exercises independently and practice worship honestly as best as possible.

One of the schools conducts enrichment outside of the scheduled activities. However, this study focuses on scheduled time activities and all the preparation activities before the learning schedule. The educative interaction syntax is divided into two types, educative interaction syntax that uses video conference app such as *Zoom Meeting* or *Google Meet* and the real-time chatting app such as *Whatsapp*. The other application is used only to support the primary activity. Besides, *Whatsapp* is also used for communication media and anticipates an obstacle related to the internet connection when a learning activity occurs. The educative interaction syntax for video conference apps is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Syntax of educative interaction on Video Conference App

Phase	Activity Steps
Preparation (through <i>Whatsapp</i>).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The teachers give information about the learning materials. 2. If the learning materials about worship exercise, the teachers will send videos or pictures containing the worship procedure. 3. The teachers ask the student to prepare themselves. 4. The teachers remind the students about manners of learning (sincere intention, neat dressing, activate the camera, and being solicitous on following teachers direction)
Introduction	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The teachers should present before the learning time is started. 2. The teachers greet the students and ask for their readiness and the condition of each student who has just come to the video conference. 3. The teachers should open the learning activity by greeting

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documentation. To get more effective learning activities, strengthening can be through motivation and self-confidence required by the students (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). Therefore, besides the skills of managing the class, the teachers should show enthusiasm and interest in running the activities.

CONCLUSION

Educative interaction in online learning can be done through various platforms. But the competence and spirits from the teachers become the primary factors in maximizing the interaction. Then, the application choice will determine the strategy that will be done. Besides, supports from infrastructure also plays an important role in enabling the online learning activity.

This study identified several schools that have done educative interaction for PAI subjects. Based on the findings, this study proposed two types of syntax for educative interaction online: the syntax of educative interaction on real-time chatting app and syntax of educative interaction on the video conference app. Every syntax has similar general phases: preparation, introduction, core, and closing. However, every phase has different details, adjusted to the service provided by the application used.

This study is preliminary research that needs further development, including identifying and formulating syntax for other applications. This study also focused on PAI learning so that further studies can be implemented on other subjects with different characteristics. The proposed syntax also needs more detailed technical procedures to be tested to more other schools to get more robust results.

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